

Case Series of Marjolin's Ulcers in Burns Scars: Unusual Acute Progression in Hilly Population of Uttarakhand

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Abstract:

Background & objectives: During the early nineteenth century, ulcer formation in long standing wounds and scars was well recorded. Soon the malignant nature of these ulcers was realised and despite the varying histology, these ulcers were grouped as Marjolin's ulcers. Since then, elaborate research was done describing these lesions. A distinctive property being long latency periods, that were reported most of the research articles. Despite this, we encountered an unusually early occurrence of malignancy in the hilly population of Uttarakhand. Hence, our objective was to do an observational study the epidemiology of Marjolin's ulcers in this population subgroup.

Methods: Epidemiological data was collected on patients reporting with Marjolin's ulcer scars from the hilly regions of Uttarakhand both in retro and prospectively.

Results: Patients from various hilly districts of Uttarakhand were evaluated. Majority had burns scar as the aetiology. All of the patients presented within 4 yrs of initial insult. Earliest was 9 months. The changes in the scar tissue were observed by the patients for which they took treatment from local physicians. The usual time of diagnosis by histopathology examination ranged from 1 month to 6 months.

Interpretation & Conclusions: In hilly population of Uttarakhand, Marjolin's transformation in scar tissue were recorded quite early as compared to data available. This is an unusual trend that is seen in this subgroup of population. As some of these patients presented with highly aggressive types, the end results were deleterious. Though the sample size was small, inaccessible hilly terrain and lack of previous studies could mask the prevalence of problem in this population.

Keywords: Marjolin's Ulcer, Latent Period, Skin Lesion, Squamous Cell Carcinoma.

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Introduction

Marjolin's ulcer is traditionally described as an, aggressive skin cancer developing in scar tissue, chronic ulcers and areas affected by inflammations. Its incidence ranges from 1-2% of all burn scars [1]. The word "ulcere cancroide" was first used in 1828 by French physician Jean Nicholas Marjolin to describe a situation in which ulcerations occur within a burn scar; the description did not specify that the ulcers were cancerous [2]. Dupuytren noted in 1838 that de novo malignancy could occur in long-term wounds; he saw this in a Belgian patient undergoing treatment for cancer that had grown out of a scar left by a burn with sulfuric acid [3]. The

name "Marjolin's ulcer" was first used by Da Costa in 1903, when he defined an ulcer arising from burn scars as Marjolin's ulcer [4]. As Marjolin first suggested, the primary cause is still old burn scars. Squamous cell carcinoma is the most common variant, and while malignant degeneration usually takes a long time called as the latency period. Other malignancies like basal cell carcinoma, melanoma, and sarcoma have also been reported in burn scars and are now included under the term Marjolin ulcer. [5,6] Latency has been described as the time between the primary pathology and the confirmation of a pathologic diagnosis of

Marjolin's ulcer. The latency period of Marjolin's ulcer is highly variable and usually ranges from 6 to 42 years. [7] Many studies have indicated latency period for the development of malignancy as late as 11 and 75 years [8]. However, we encountered an unusually early occurrence of malignancy i.e. a very short latency period, in the hilly population of Uttarakhand. The malignancy was encountered in scars as early as 9 months of initial insult. Very few cases of such acute transformations, have been reported in the literature. [9,10,11] Here is an epidemiological record of 11 such cases from various Districts of Uttarakhand.

Material and Methods

Ethical clearance was taken from ethics committee. Consent was taken from all patients involved. Epidemiological data was collected on patients reporting with Marjolin's ulcer scars. Patients reporting from other parts country were excluded from study. A total of 11 cases were enlisted who presented from 2021 to 2024. The presenting complaint, time since injury, histological type, and treatment given was recorded.

Data and Results

3 were male and 8 were female patients. Out of total patients, 4 had thermal (Fig.1), 2 had electrical burns (Fig.2), 2 had unstable surgical scars while rest of 2 had trophic ulcers (Fig.3). All patients who had early onset of malignancy were hailing from hilly districts of Uttarakhand like Rudraprayag, Chamoli, Uttarkashi, Tehri and Pauri. As far as histological type was concerned, all were squamous cell carcinomas. Most of them were highly differentiated malignancies of less aggressive nature, but 2 cases showed poorly differentiated aggressive types. All of the patients presented within 4 yrs of initial insult. Earliest was 9 months. The changes in the scar tissue were observed by the patients for which they took treatment from local physicians. The usual time of diagnosis by histopathology examination ranged from 1 month to 6 months. Out of 11 patients, 7 underwent wide local excision and flap reconstruction (Fig. 4a,4b,4c). Whereas, 3 patients landed in amputation. (Table 1)

Table 1: Epidemiology, pathological subtypes, latent periods of Marjolin's lesions.

Sr. No.	Etiology	District	Age	Sex	Area of body involved	Histopath Type	Time since insult	Time since changes observed	Procedure done
1	Thermal Burns	Chamoli	60	F	Foot ulcer	SCC HD	4yrs	5mths	amputation
2	Bedsore	Rudraprayag	32	F	Ischium	SCC PD	30mths	1mth	WLE Flap coverage
3	Hernia Surgical Scar	Uttarkashi	65	M	Abdomen	SCC HD	18 mths	4 mths	WLE Flap coverage
4	Thermal Burns	Tehri	45	M	Popleteal Fossa	SCC HD	2.5yrs	2mths	WLE Flap coverage
5	Thermal Burns	Tehri	57	F	Popleteal Fossa	SCC HD	20 mths	6 mths	amputation
6	Trophic Ulcer	Pauri	25	M	Foot/Sole	SCC PD	9 mths	5 mths	amputation
7	Breast Abscess	Rudraprayag	33	F	Breast	SCC HD	3.5 yrs	2.5 mths	WLE Flap coverage
8	Hernia Surgical Scar	Pauri	65	M	Abdomen	SCC HD	17mths	3 mths	WLE Flap coverage
9	Electric Burn	Chamoli	55	F	Scalp	SCC HD	3.5yrs	3 mths	WLE Flap coverage
10	Electric Burns	Tehri	68	F	Scalp	SCC HD	2.5mths	2mths	WLE Flap coverage
11	Thermal Burns	Chamoli	32	F	Elbow	SCC HD	3 yrs	6 mths	WLE Joint arthrodesis

Clinical Images

Figure 1: Burns scar malignancy

Figure 2: Electrical exit wound on heel presented with Marjolin's ulcer

Figure 3: Trophic ulcer with malignant changes

Figure 4A: Marjolin's ulcer over greater trochanter (previous pressure sore)

Figure 4B: Defect after excision

Figure 4C: Flap coverage for defect.

Discussion

Carcinomas arising in an area of scar or chronic irritation have been studied over the years. Many theories have been developed to explain the pathogenesis of chronic nonhealing wounds' malignant transformation. Since 1930, it has been

suggested that decreased vascularity combined with weakened epithelium creates a susceptibility of nonhealing chronic wounds to carcinogens. [12] Dvork proposed that prolonged attempts at wound healing parallel the generation of tumor stroma and that the development of cellular atypia in the

wound healing process might lead to malignancy. [13]

As cited by Treves and Pack, Virchow proposed that chronic mechanical or solar irritation was responsible for initiating carcinogenesis. [14] Menkin studied the role of inflammation and proposed that in genetically susceptible persons, exudates produced by endogenous growth-promoting factors can act as cocarcinogens. Elevated expression of proto-oncogenes has been suggested as a mechanism for malignant degeneration in Marjolin's ulcers. [15,16] The Indian Kangri burn cancer and the Japanese Kairo burn cancer have shown that skin cancer is correlated with chronic or recurrent thermal injury. Both follow the use of hot coals in utensils applied to the abdomen in order to provide heat. According to the findings of other studies, lymphocyte movement in chronic wounds may be impeded by the avascular scar tissue. This change may impair immune surveillance and result in the inability to recognize non-self-malignancy in its early stages. To date, no concrete mechanism for the development of Marjolin's ulcers in burns or other wound types has been discovered.

Marjolin's ulcer is typically diagnosed by means of pathologic interpretation of a tissue biopsy specimen. Unfortunately, confounding characteristics of both benign and malignant ulcers can result in the delay of biopsy and formal diagnosis. The transformation from ulcer to malignant disease is typically slow, with latency periods averaging 29 years based on the 443 patients reviewed by Kerr-Valentic et al. [17] Due to this lengthy latent period, the majority of patients present at a mean age of 52 years later in life. Despite this lengthy progression to malignant disease, Marjolin's ulcers tend to be more aggressive than other forms of skin cancers, with a metastasis rate of 27.5 percent in current world literature.

The potential for development in many different wound types and anatomical locations, combined with the difficulty of diagnosis without a biopsy, can delay proper treatment in many cases. Marjolin's ulcer seems to have a predilection for disadvantaged patients with limited access to health care, resulting from burns and other wounds being neglected. [15] The majority of reported cases come from developing countries, where patients have a greater tendency to delayed presentation.

Treatment for Marjolin's ulcer is quite varied. Following burns and other severe injuries, it is critical to provide prompt and permanent wound coverage in order to prevent wound progression into squamous cell carcinoma. Leaving large wounds to heal by secondary intention creates the potential for a chronic nonhealing ulcer and the

ideal conditions for development of a Marjolin's ulcer. Wide local excision and subsequent skin grafting appears to be the standard of care for most authors. [18,19,20] Flap coverage may be required. The late presentation and advanced clinical stage of many patients from developing countries produced tumor characteristics that could be treated only with amputation. [21,22]

Conclusion

Marjolin's changes in chronic scars is quite common. In hilly population of Uttarakhand, Marjolin's transformation in scar tissue were recorded quite early as compared to usual incidence. Malignant changes, are also encountered in young population. These at times are highly aggressive types and therefore salvage and reconstruction are extremely difficult resulting in repeated surgeries and at times amputations.

Hence, high index of suspicion is detrimental in early diagnosis and treatment. These cases support the clinical guideline that any nonhealing wound, acute or chronic, should be biopsied and sent for pathologic examination to ensure that it does not represent a Marjolin's ulcer.

Also any raw area should be resurfaced as quickly as possible. Though the sample size was small, inaccessible hilly terrain and lack of previous studies could mask the prevalence of problem in this population.

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